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Effect of Guided Discovery Teaching Method under Individualized Learning Condition on Performance in Trigonometry among Senior Secondary Students in Katsina State, Nigeria

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***Abstract:** This study investigated the effect of guided discovery teaching method under individualized learning condition on performance in trigonometry among senior secondary students in Katsina Zonal Education Quality Assurance (KZEQA), Katsina State. The research adopted quasi-experimental design of the pretest post-test nonequivalent control group type. To guide the study, two specific objectives and two research questions were formulated and two corresponding null hypotheses tested. A 25 – item instrument, the Trigonometry Performance Test (TPT), having a reliability coefficient of 0.832 was employed to collect data from a sample of 123 students (67 males and 56 females). The data collected was analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics with the mean and standard deviation employed for answering the research questions while the ANCOVA and independent samples *t*-test were used to test the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. Findings of the study indicate that the students taught trigonometry using guided discovery teaching method under individualized learning significantly performed better than their counterparts taught same concepts using the lecture method; and that the male students taught trigonometry using guided discovery teaching method under individualized learning significantly performed better than their female counterparts. It was concluded that the guided discovery teaching method under the individualized learning condition has the potential of enhancing secondary school students' performance in trigonometry. Therefore, the study recommends that secondary school mathematics teachers should utilize guided discovery teaching method when teaching trigonometry.*

***Key words:** Guided Discovery Teaching Method, Individualized Learning Condition, Performance, Trigonometry.*

Introduction

Mathematics can be regarded as a cornerstone subject as it fosters critical thinking, logical reasoning, and problem-solving skills which are essential across various fields like science, engineering, and technology (Hillmayr et al., 2020). It serves as the bedrock of knowledge and a catalyst for creativity, enabling innovative problem-solving approaches (Olaoye et al., 2023). By equipping learners with the ability to make informed decisions, analyze data, and predict outcomes crucial for success in the contemporary world, mathematics builds in pupils uniquely powerful ways of describing analysis which lead to changing the world for the better (Setidisho, 2016). It can stimulate moments of pleasure and wonder for all students when they solve a problem for the first time, discover a more elegant solution or notice hidden connections (Ale, 2009). Students who are functionally capable can think independently in applied and abstract ways and can reason, solve problem and assess risks. (Usman et al., 2023). It is thus not surprising that stakeholders in education attach considerable importance to the subject.

Despite the importance attached to mathematics by all stakeholders in education, senior secondary school students still perform poorly in the subject. This has been attributed to many factors, amongst which is poor or inappropriate teaching methods (Abiodun, 2020). However, mathematics teaching demands that teachers use appropriate teaching methods that will give their students opportunity to be actively involved in teaching – learning process. Teaching methods, according to Sunday et al. (2021) can broadly be categorized into two, viz: expository and heuristic. The expository methods, also referred to as conventional methods, are largely teacher centered where learners passively acquire knowledge as the teacher teaches and the students take notes without them being involved in class activities (Sunday et. al, 2021). On the other hand, the heuristic methods of teaching are learner centered, where learners are actively involved in the learning process (Sunday et. al, 2021). In this method, learning is through inquiry and it is where flexibility and creativity are encouraged.

Esan (2015) observed that mathematics teachers in secondary schools largely use the expository method. According to Esan (2015), a number of problems which have been identified concerning this method of teaching include passivity of students, lack of collaborative learning and emphasis on theory. Ndukwe (2018) posits that when teaching method is inappropriate for the level of students, the result is likely to be poor performance and dislike of the subject. It is therefore not surprising that students are underperforming in the mathematics. This goes to show that use of appropriate teaching methods is the keys to success and progress of students in the subject.

In Nigeria, the mathematics curriculum for basic and post basic schools recommends the use of guided, discovery, laboratory, demonstration, discussion, cooperative learning methods among others for teaching (National Education and Research Development Council (NERDC)). However, the curriculum did not specify which areas or topics should be taught using a particular teaching method. Since the heuristic methods are learner-centered, with many advantages, this study sets out investigate the effect of guided discovery teaching method (GDTM) under individualized learning condition on performance in trigonometry among senior secondary students' in Katsina state.

With the GDTM, students are enabled to arrive at new knowledge as a result of their own observations may be as individuals or groups (Akerson et al., 2017). In this study, the individualized learning condition was focused upon. The method provides for activities which permit self-direction, exploration, the nurturing and satisfying of curiosity on the part of the students. It is an avenue for the students to find out things themselves using existing and established rules and principles, thus enhancing the development of their critical thinking capabilities.

Trigonometry was the focused of this research work because secondary school students have phobia for this area of mathematics to the extent that many of them do avoid trigonometry related questions in both internal and external examinations (WAEC May/June Chief examiners report 2016 – 2020). As an aspect of mathematics that is used to calculate the lengths of the sides of triangles as well as the angles between those sides (Mathijs, 2017), trigonometry is also commonly used in finding the heights of tower and mountains in our society; it is usually used for navigation to find the distance of shore from a point in a sea. In our everyday construction, trigonometric ideas are used to determine areas of walls, door and window frames, and roofing materials.

Trigonometry is an area that has very wide practical applications in the lives of human beings and therefore very important. Thus, it was posited that using the GDTM under individualized learning condition to teach trigonometry will enable each student to arrive at new knowledge as a result of observations made at the individual level. This is posited on the fact that the method provides for activities which permit self-direction, exploration, the nurturing and satisfying of curiosity on the part of the students. Despite these positive effects of the GDTM, there is paucity of research on whether the method should be deployed under the individualized or group learning conditions. Therefore, more research is needed on the type of learning condition to be adopted when incorporating the method into daily our classroom lessons.

In discussing the factors affecting students' performance in mathematics, gender which refers to the social or cultural construct, characteristics, behaviors and role which society ascribes to males and females (Okeke, 2017) is usually taken into cognisance. As a socio – cultural construct, gender related issues in mathematics have continued to receive serious attention judging by the quantum of studies done to that effect. In this regard Ogunleye (2022) observed that, although the numbers of female scientists have increased, yet gender equality has not been achieved. He (Ogunleye, 2022) argued that in Nigeria, harder tasks are assigned to males while females are given the relatively easy and less demanding tasks. Consequently, the effect of gender when the guide discovery method is used to teach trigonometry under individualized learning condition was also focused upon.

The research was restricted to only public schools in Katsina Zonal Education Quality Assurance (KZEQA) of Katsina State because the proportion of underperforming students in these schools far outnumbered those of the private schools, a situation which can be considered as not to have justified the huge public funds being expended on them. The study was limited to co-educational schools that have senior secondary II (SSII) classes because this set of students are more stable school in addition to being reasonably exposed to mathematics concepts in the senior secondary school syllabus. Thus, only the content of the SSII mathematics syllabus for the third term (2022/2023 session) was used to carry out the research work.

Conceptual Framework

As a student centered and activity-oriented teaching strategy, the GDTM enables the teacher to deploy varieties of instructional materials and probing questions to enable students discover answers to problems at hand. In using this method, students learn through personal experiences with limited subtle guidance from their teachers by way of using thought provoking questions (Davidson, 2010). It allows interactions between teachers and their students, on one hand and amongst students themselves, on the other hand. GDTM encourages independence which makes learning more memorable and therefore possessing the capacity to promote critical thinking. This method places the teacher as an overseer and facilitator of learning as well as the mediator between students and instructional materials. Therefore,

GDTM entails that learners must be guided along a path toward discovery of ideas, concepts and information. This requires two things:

1. A learning design that builds an ever-increasing understanding and comprehension in learners without causing frustration or apathy.
2. A learning facilitator who guides rather than teaches during the learning activities. The facilitator provides initial guidance, monitors progress, steers learners back on track where necessary, asks questions to ensure understanding, facilitates feedback when required, gives positive reinforcement and helps learners integrate concepts into the tasks they are undertaking.

GDTM can be incorporated into lecture, laboratory and field courses. They are ideal cooperative learning activities. It also fits beautifully into the exploration phase of the learning cycle approach of teaching (Brown & Abel, 2017) and are especially effective when they are assigned before any lectures or readings on the topic. Because the GDTM can be time consuming while still fostering deep learning, they are best used to teach course material that is especially important, conceptually difficult, or counter-intuitive. In order to succeed, GDTM must be adequately scaffolded so that students remain within their zone of proximal development, the zone between what they can do on their own and what they cannot do, even with help (Lasmawan & Budiarta, 2020).

When using the GDTM, learning takes place in problem-solving situations where learners draw on their own experiences and prior knowledge to discover the truths that are to be learned. It is therefore posited herein that students are more likely to remember concepts they discover on their own than those they are taught. This teaching method certainly aligns with one of the goals of teaching and learning which demands integration of personal experiences about our world which is expected to lead to knowledge development and skills acquisition necessary for enhanced performance.

Performance is the measure of students' learning or acquisition of certain skills at the end of a certain period teaching and learning session. Due to the importance of performance in school programmes, various educators gave their definitions of performances. According to Marshall (2011), it is the extent to which a person has achieved something, acquires certain information or mastered certain skills, usually as result of planned instruction or training. Bakare (2015) sees performance as relative to some standards and he further states that performance and other dimensions of learning can be measured by a variety of yardsticks or measuring instruments, including test scores, ranks or grades and is usually associated with mental success. Achino (2010) considers performance to be the level of an individual's educational growth in a test when compared with the scores of others of the same level. Akindele (2013) viewed performance as what students have been able to gain at the end of a given period of instruction. Thus, it could be discerned that performance is essentially applied to what an individual can do within a specific criterion domain as assessed by outcomes.

Performance of students in process skills acquisition has also been investigated over the years. Okebukola (2005) revealed that science students generally exhibit low acquisition of science process skills. It might be that teachers and students are not using appropriate teaching methods and in some instances, when used, it is used effectively. Considering the close affinity between the effective use of appropriate teaching methods and students' performance, it is conceptualized in this study that the deployment of the GDTM under the individualized learning condition to teach trigonometry will enhance students' performance, irrespective of gender difference, in not only this area of mathematics but in the subject as a whole. This conceptualized is represented by the conceptual framework diagram shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework Diagram

Theoretical Framework

The Social Constructivist theory propounded by Lev Vygotsky (1896-1934) propounded was adopted to provide the theoretical underpinning for this study. This theory holds that learning is a collaborative process. According to Vygotsky, the development of a students' intelligence results from social interaction in the world and that speech, social interaction and co-operative activity are all important aspects of the social world. The Social Constructivist theory, which emphasizes the importance of collaboration in leaning, argued that all cognitive functions originate in, and must therefore be explained as products of social interactions and that learning is not simply the assimilation and accommodation of new knowledge by learners, it is the process by which learners are integrated into the knowledge community.

Vygotsky distinguished between two developmental levels; the level of actual development and that of potential development, which he referred to as the zone of proximal development. While the first refers to the level of development that the learner has already reached which is the level at which the learner is capable of solving problems independently, the latter refers to the level of development that the learner is capable of reaching under the guidance of teachers or in collaboration with peers. Vygotsky's theory holds that as a result of collaboration, the learner is capable of solving problems and understanding material at the zone of proximal development which he/she was not capable of solving and understanding at the level of actual development. The theory therefore posits that the level of potential development is the level at which learning takes place. Owing to this theory's supposition of how learning takes place is, it is believed in this study that the GDTM possesses considerably high potentials of enhancing performance when properly and effectively deployed.

Review of Related Empirical Studies

A number of empirical studies related to this study were encountered during literature review. Some of these studies include those of Luntungan (2012), Akanmu and Fajemidagba (2013), Luzviminda, et al. (2015), Bamidele and Ariyo (2017), and Abari and Ikyule (2021).

Luntungan (2012) explored the effects of guided and conventional teaching methods in business instruction and students' attitude toward the class on students' performance. The respondents were 135 college students from an Indonesian university. Both the experimental and the comparison groups took the same course taught in two different sections. For two weeks, one teacher taught the two sections of the same course using different teaching methods. In the experimental group containing fifty-eight (n=58) students, the teacher used direct small group activities and lectured in the comparison group (n=77). Two-way ANCOVA statistics and t-tests were used to test null hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. The results showed that while both teaching methods had a significant effect on students' performance, the small group study group performed better. The results also showed that students' attitude toward the class did not affect performance; however, students' attitude were affected by the teaching methods used in the class. Luntungan's (2012) study and this study are related in that some of the variables (i.e., GDTM and performance), research design (i.e., quasi – experimental design),

statistical tools (i.e. ANCOVA and t – test) and result (i.e., better performance of the study group) are the same.

Akanmu and Fajemidagba (2013) investigated the effect of guided-discovery learning strategy on students' performance in Mathematics alongside influence of gender and scoring levels ability of the students. 202 SSI Students from two selected public co-educational schools in Ejigbo Local Government Area of Osun State constituted the sample of the study. The research was a quasi-experimental one and the main instrument for data collection was a 20-item multiple choice Mathematics Achievement Test drawn from West African Examination Council past questions on Set Theory. Three research questions were raised with three corresponding hypotheses tested. Results revealed a significant difference in favour of those exposed to guided-discovery learning strategy compared to those not taught using guided-discovery learning strategy. Akanmu and Fajemidagba's (2013) study is related to this study in that two of the variables (i.e., GDTM and performance), the research designs (i.e., quasi – experimental design), source of items used in the research instrument (i.e., West African Examination Council past questions) and result (i.e., better performance of the guided-discovery learning strategy) are the same.

Luzviminda, et al. (2015) examine the effect of group guided discovery approach on the performance of students in Geometry of Malinta National High School for school year 2012- 2013. The study used the quasi- experimental approach with non-equivalent control group pretest/posttest design. The sample of the study consisted of 92 students, half of whom were taught using the group guided discovery approach, and the other half using the traditional lecture approach of teaching. The experiment lasted for two months during the fourth grading period. To determine the mathematical performances between the defined groups the percentage, mean, and the t- test for dependent and independent means were used. The study showed that the performance in Geometry of those students taught using group guided discovery was significantly higher than those students taught using the traditional lecture approach. Thus, the study concluded that group guided discovery approach was more effective than the traditional approach. This study (Luzviminda, et al., 2015) is related to the current study from the view point of the fact that two of the variables (i.e., GDTM and performance), the research designs (i.e., quasi- experimental approach with non-equivalent control group pretest/posttest quasi – experimental design), population of the study (i.e., senior secondary school students), one of the statistical tools used for data analysis (i.e., t – test), subject area on which the study was performed (i.e., mathematics) and result (i.e., better performance of the guided-discovery approach) are the same.

Bamidele and Ariyo (2017) compared the performance of male and female students in Chemistry when taught with guided discovery and demonstration teaching techniques in senior secondary schools. The study adopted a non-equivalent control group pretest/posttest quasi – experimental design. The population for the study consisted of Chemistry students in senior secondary schools in Ile-Ife. The sample consisted of Eighty-four (84) students from three schools in Ife Central Local Government Area of Osun State which were selected using simple random sampling technique. One intact class each was used. Two instruments, Chemistry Achievement Test (CAT) and Questionnaire on Attitudes of Students towards Chemistry (QASTC), were utilized for the study. Data collected were analyzed using Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) and Analysis of Variance (ANOVA). The results showed that, there was a significant difference in the performance of students exposed to guided discovery, demonstration teaching technique and those exposed to teacher expository teaching technique ($F=123.972$; $p<0.05$). The findings also showed that, there was a significant difference in the performance of male and female Chemistry students exposed to guided discovery and demonstration teaching

techniques ($F= 12.04$; $p< 0.05$). This showed that male and female students performed better when exposed to guide discovery teaching techniques. This study (Bamidele & Ariyo, 2017) is related to the current study from the view point of the fact that two of the variables (i.e., GDTM and performance), the research designs (i.e., quasi- experimental approach with non-equivalent control group pretest/posttest quasi – experimental design), population of the study (i.e., senior secondary school students), one of the statistical tools used for data analysis (i.e., ANCOVA) and result (i.e., better performance of the guided-discovery teaching technique) are the same.

Abari and Ikyule (2021) investigated the effect of guided discovery approach on Students' Academic Achievement in Mathematics in Senior Secondary Schools in Ushongo Local Government Area, Benue state, Nigeria with a view to establishing whether or not guided- discovery teaching approach would have effect on students' achievement in Mathematics. The study raised two specific objectives, two research questions and two related null hypotheses. 120 students were randomly selected for the study as the sample. The instrument for the study was mathematics achievement test. Research questions were answered using mean and standard deviation while analysis of covariance (ANCOVA) was employed in testing null hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. The findings revealed no significant difference in mean achievement scores of students taught mathematics using Guided-discovery teaching method and those taught with lecture method. The findings also revealed no significant difference in mean achievement scores of male and female students taught Mathematics using Guided discovery approach. Abari and Ikyule's (2021) study is related to the current study from the view point of the fact that two of the variables (i.e., GDTM and performance/achievement), the research designs (i.e., quasi- experimental approach with non-equivalent control group pretest/posttest quasi – experimental design), population of the study (i.e., senior secondary school students), some of the statistical tools used for data analysis (i.e., mean and standard deviation, and ANCOVA) and subject area on which the study was performed (i.e., mathematics) are the same.

It could therefore be seen that while these related empirical studies reviewed had many similarities with the present study, none investigated the effect of guided inquiry under individualized learning condition and none was conducted in the same study area with the same population segment, which constitutes some of the gaps that the current study intends to filled.

Statement of the Problem

In spite of the support given to the education of secondary school students by both state and federal governments in Nigeria, a substantial number of students either do not or partially achieve the aims of secondary school education as a result of poor performance. Charles-Ogan (2017) observes that secondary students' mathematics performance is less than 50 percent for the past decades. Statistics of the results of Katsina State students' mathematics performance in West African Secondary School Certificate Examination (WASSCE) from 2011 to 2020 revealed that the overall performance of the students at the Senior Secondary Certificate Examination (SSCE) has been poor, as evidenced in Table 1.

Table 1. Students Performance in Mathematics in May/June WASSEC (2011-2020) in Katsina State

Performance of the Students					
Year	No. of Students	Credit Pass & Above (A1 – C6)		Below Credit Pass (D7 – F9)	
		N	%	N	%
2011	36,798	478	1.30	36,320	98.70
2012	38,602	494	1.28	38,108	98.72

2013	41,758	4,342	10.40	37,416	89.60
2014	43,065	4,421	10.27	38,644	89.73
2015	44,439	5,566	12.53	38,873	87.47
2016	20,404	7,790	38.18	12,614	61.82
2017	21,717	11,612	53.47	10,105	46.53
2018	23,916	7,188	30.06	16,728	69.94
2019	21,589	7,276	33.70	14,313	66.30
2020	22,884	9,313	40.70	13,571	59.30
Total	315,172	58,480	18.55	256,692	81.45

Source: (WAEC Katsina State Annual Report, 2011-2020).

It could be seen that except for the year 2017, students with credit pass and above (A1 – C6) has remained below 50% throughout the period. In mathematics, students' poor performance has been attributed to many factors but majorly amongst these factors is poor teaching methods. Due to individual differences of the students, mathematics teachers owe it as a duty to employ varieties of teaching methods and techniques in order to offset the problem of boredom and abstractness of the subject and more importantly enhance understanding of what is being taught. Unfortunately, many mathematics teachers find it difficult to change their mode of delivery. They stick to the lecture method and most of the times give explanations that are too complicated for the students to relate to life experiences. It is therefore not surprising that the issue of poor performance among students in secondary school mathematics has continued to persist.

The instructional methods employed teachers play an important role in the students' acquisition of content. Therefore, the search for appropriate teaching methods and techniques will continue to be issues of necessity. Students centered or activity-based methods like the GDTM can lead students out of failure in mathematics if properly used by teachers. It is on this basis that the study investigated the effect of GDTM under individualized condition on performance in trigonometry among secondary school students in KZEQA, Katsina State.

Objectives of the Study

To determine the difference between pretest and posttest mean performance scores of the:

1. students taught trigonometry using GDTM under individualized learning condition and their counterparts taught same concepts using lecture method;
2. male and female students taught trigonometry using GDTM under individualized learning condition.

Research Questions

1. What is the difference between pretest and posttest mean performance scores of the students taught trigonometry using GDTM under individualized learning condition and their counterparts taught same concepts using lecture method?
2. What is the difference between pretest and posttest mean performance scores of the male and female students taught trigonometry using GDTM under individualized learning condition?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were tested at .05 level of significance:

H01: There is no significant difference between the mean performance scores of the students taught trigonometry using GDTM under individualized learning condition and their counterparts taught same concepts using lecture method;

H02: There is no significant between the mean performance scores of the male and female students taught trigonometry using GDTM under individualized learning condition.

Research Design

The quasi-experimental design of the pre-test, post-test non-randomize control group type was adopted for the study. This design was considered suitable because the study setting does not permit random assignment of subjects to both experimental and control groups. In other words, there was no random assignment of the students to the two treatment groups. Rather, intact classes were used. The experimental group was exposed to the teaching of trigonometry using GDTM under individualized learning condition while the control group was taught same concept using the lecture method.

Population, Sample and Sampling Procedure

The population of the study was made up of all the 17572 senior secondary II (SSII) students (10258 males and 7314 females) in Katsina Zonal Education Quality Assurance (KZEQA). There are 25 public senior secondary schools (21 co-educational and four singled-sexed schools with two being purely male and two being purely female) from the three local governments (LGs) (Katsina, Jibia and Kaita) under KZEQA. The average age of the students is 17yrs. These schools are owned by the Katsina State Government and they operate as either day or boarding schools. 123 students, with the experimental and control groups comprising of 65 (35 males and 30 females) and 58 (32 males and 26 females) respectively, were selected using the cluster and random sampling technique. Schools in each of the three LGs were considered as a cluster where two LGs were randomly selected and as well assigned to the experimental and control groups. From each group, one school was randomly selected. Thereafter, one intact SS II class was randomly selected.

The Research Instrument

A 25 – item instrument, the Trigonometry performance Test (TPT), was used to collect data for the study. Items of the TPT were adopted from past WAEC, NECO and JAMB questions on Trigonometry. Each item is a multiple-choice objective question type with four options out of which one is the correct answer. The TPT was validated by experts in mathematics education, mathematics and educational measurement and evaluation. The TPT was pilot tested using the test – retest method where a reliability coefficient of 0.832 was found, signifying that the instrument is quite reliable for the study.

Data Collection and Analysis Procedure

Both the experimental and control groups were subjected to pre-testing sessions before treatment. The treatment sessions entailed exposing the experimental group to the teaching of Trigonometry using the GDTM under the individualized learning condition while the control group was taught same concepts using the lecture method. Both teaching sessions, which lasted for six weeks, covered Bearing and Distance, and Angles of Elevation and Depression. Thereafter, a posttest was administered.

Data collected was analyzed using descriptive statistics of mean, standard deviation and standard error of the mean in order to answer the research questions while inferential statistics of ANCOVA and independent samples t – test analysis were used to test the null hypotheses one and two respectively, at the .05 level of significance.

Results

Performance of the students taught trigonometry using GDTM under the individualized learning condition and Lecture Methods

Table 1. Analysis of the Pretest and Posttest Mean Performance Scores of Experimental and Control Groups

Test	Group	N	Mean	SEM	SD	MD
Pretest	Experimental Group (GDTM under individualized learning condition)	65	16.25	0.479	3.865	- 0.23
	Control Group (Lecture Method)	58	16.48	0.531	4.04	
Post- test	Experimental Group (GDTM under individualized learning condition)	65	67.97	1.166	9.397	10.11
	Control Group (Lecture Method)	58	57.86	0.683	5.203	

Table 1 shows that the difference between the pretest mean performance scores of the students taught trigonometry using Guided discovery under individualized learning condition ($M = 16.25$, $SD = 3.865$) and those taught same concept using the lecture method ($M = 16.48$, $SD = 4.40$) is $- 0.23$ in favor of the students in the lecture method group. However, the difference between the posttest mean performance scores of the students taught trigonometry using guided discovery under individualized learning condition ($M = 67.97$, $SD = 9.397$) and those taught same concept using the lecture method ($M = 57.86$, $SD = 5.203$) is 10.11 in favor of the students in guided discovery under individualized learning condition group.

Table 2. ANCOVA of Performance of students taught trigonometry using the GDTM under individualized condition and their counterparts taught same concepts using the lecture method

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Partial Eta Squared
Corrected Model	3160.695 ^a	2	1580.348	26.467	.000	.306
Intercept	24679.783	1	24679.783	413.326	.000	.775
Pretest	29.611	1	29.611	.496	.483	.004
Group	3146.615	1	3146.615	52.698	.000	.305
Error	7165.224	120	59.710			
Total	501668.000	123				
Corrected Total	10325.919	122				

a. R Squared = .306 (Adjusted R Squared = .295)

Table 2 shows that the difference between the performance of the students taught trigonometry using the GDTM under individualized condition and their counterparts taught same concepts using the lecture method is significant ($F(1, 120) = 52.698$, $p < .05$, *partial eta*

$squared = .305$). This indicates that the students taught trigonometry using the GDTM under individualized condition significantly performed better than their counterparts taught same concepts using the lecture method

Performance of the male and female students taught trigonometry using GDTM under the individualized learning condition

Table 3. Analysis of Post test Mean Performance of the male and female students taught trigonometry using GDTM under the individualized learning condition

Gender	N	Mean	SD	SEM	MD	Df	T	Sig.
Male	35	70.69	9.591	1.621				
					5.89	63	2.631	.011*
Female	30	64.80	8.231	1.503				

*Significant at $p \leq .05$

From Table 3, it could be seen that the difference between the posttest mean performance scores of the Male ($M = 70.69$, $SD = 9.591$) and Female ($M = 64.80$, $SD = 8.231$) taught trigonometry using GDTM under individualized learning condition is 5.89 in favor of the male students and that this difference is significant ($t(63) = 2.631$, $p < .05$).

Summary of Major Findings

1. The students taught trigonometry using GDTM under individualized learning significantly performed better than their counterparts taught same concept using the lecture method.
2. The male students taught trigonometry using GDTM under individualized learning significantly performed better than their female counterparts.

Discussion

The findings of this study are similar and dissimilar to a number of research findings. The first finding of is in line with those of Akanmu and Fajemidagba (2013), Matthew and Igharo (2023), Luzviminda, et al. (2015) and Popoola and Joshua (2021). Akanmu and Fajemidagba (2013), who investigated the effect of guided-discovery learning strategy on students' performance in Mathematics alongside influence of gender and scoring levels ability of the students, found significant difference in favour of those exposed to guided-discovery learning strategy compared to those not taught using the strategy. Matthew and Igharo (2023) examined the achievement levels of two groups of senior secondary school students who were taught a difficult concept in further mathematics using the guided inquiry teaching method and the conventional teaching method. They (Matthew and Igharo, 2023) found that the students who were taught with the guided inquiry teaching method had better achievement scores than students who were taught using the conventional teaching method.

Luzviminda, et al. (2015) examine the effect of group guided discovery approach on the performance of students in geometry of Malinta National High School for school year 2012-2013 and found that the group guided discovery approach was more effective than the traditional approach. Also, Popoola and Joshua (2021) examined the effects of modelling and guided discovery on secondary school students' performance in mathematics in Ekiti State. Their (Popoola & Joshua, 2021) result revealed that the use of modeling, guided-discovery and conventional strategies enhanced performance of students in Mathematics, with guided-discovery strategy being the most effective strategy.

On the other hand, the findings of Abari and Ikyule (2021) and Tella and Ogundiya (2022) differ from the first finding. Abari and Ikyule (2021), who investigated the effect of guided discovery approach on students' academic achievement in mathematics in senior secondary schools in Ushongo local government area, Benue state, Nigeria., found no significant difference in mean achievement scores of students taught mathematics using guided discovery teaching method and those taught with lecture method. Also, Tella and Ogundiya (2022) determined the effects of concept mapping and guided discovery instructional strategies on student's learning achievement in Redox concept in Chemistry in Oyo State, Nigeria and found no significant two- way interaction effect of treatment and gender on student's achievement in Redox concept of chemistry.

The second finding of the study is similar to the findings of Akanmu and Fajemidagba (2013), Ozomadu (2015), Bamidele and Ariyo (2017), and Adeagbo, Okereke, Ademiluyi and Umoru (2019). Akanmu and Fajemidagba (2013) investigated the effect of guided-discovery learning strategy on students' performance in mathematics alongside influence of gender and scoring levels ability of the students and found that both male and female students performed equally well when taught using guided discovery strategy. Ozomadu (2015) compared the effectiveness of guided discovery and expository methods on Senior Secondary II (SS II) mathematics students' achievement. He (Ozomadu, 2015) found significant gender difference in the effectiveness of GDTM in enhancing the mathematics achievement of the students.

Bamidele and Ariyo (2017) compared the performance of students in Chemistry when taught with guided discovery and demonstration teaching techniques in senior secondary schools. Their (Bamidele and Ariyo, 2017) findings revealed significant difference in the performance of male and female Chemistry students exposed to guided discovery and demonstration teaching techniques. Also, Adeagbo, Okereke, Ademiluyi and Umoru (2019) examined the effects of guided discovery teaching strategy on performance of financial accounting students in Oyo state, Nigeria and found that there was significant difference between performance of male and female students taught accounting using guided discovery teaching strategy.

On the other hand, the findings of Abari and Ikyule(2021), Popoola and Joshua (2021), Uwak and Stephen (2020), and Tella and Ogundiya (2022) contradict the second findings of the study. Abari and Ikyule (2021) investigated the effect of guided discovery approach on Students' Academic Achievement in Mathematics in Senior Secondary Schools in Ushongo Local Government Area, Benue state, Nigeria, with a view to establishing whether or not guided-discovery teaching approach would have effect on students' achievement in Mathematics. Their (Abari & Ikyule, 2021) study revealed no significant difference in mean achievement scores of male and female students taught Mathematics using guided discovery approach. Popoola and Joshua (2021) examined the effects of modelling and guided discovery on secondary school students' performance in mathematics in Ekiti State, Nigeria and found that modeling and guided-discovery strategies are not gender biased.

Uwak and Stephen (2020) examined the effect of demonstration and GDTMs of teaching on the secondary school physics students' achievement in Ibiono Ibom Local Government Area, Akwa Ibom state, Nigeria found that gender recorded no significant difference on the students' achievement. Tella and Ogundiya (2022) determined the effects of concept mapping and guided discovery instructional strategies on student's learning achievement in Redox concept in Chemistry in Oyo State, Nigeria. They (Uwak & Stephen, 2020) found no significant main effect of gender on the student's achievement.

Conclusion and Recommendations

The findings of the study indicate that despite GDTM under the individualized learning condition being more favourable to male students, it still proves to be more effective than the lecture method in enhancing senior secondary students' performance in trigonometry. Consequently, it is hereby recommended that mathematics teachers should use the GDTM when teaching trigonometry. Also, teachers in training should be equipped with knowledge vast enough to implement GDTMs of teaching mathematics.

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